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EVALUATION OF MOBILE DIARY TOOL'S RECORDING MEDIA FOR SELF-REPORTING IN OBSERVATIONAL SITUATIONS

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ABSTRACT

As part of the design process, researchers and designers have been exploring the potential value of incorporating user experiences into the development of new technology. They have long recognized the need for an assessment method; for a tool to obtain an accurate record of the user life experiences that are the most important for judging the utility of a technology. Experience Sampling Method (ESM) is a methodological approach that allows research participants to provide reports of their behavior and their cognitive and emotional states a number of times, just as they occur in the participants' natural environment. We provided a mobile phone application coupled with ESM to support collecting data in different media formats for subject self-reporting. The primary purpose of this study was to understand how the media used in different observational situations affect the self-reporting of subjects, and to clarify the full constellation of subject responses and behavior as they relate to conditions in the field.

Keywords: ESM, Self-reporting, Activity Probes .

INTRODUCTION

The user experience is an important element in the design process. Understanding the user's actual experiences helps the designer recognize the user's pattern of behavior, thoughts and emotions, in ways essential to developing highly functional interactive products. (Randall, Harper, & Rouncefield, 2007) In recent years, the examination of the user experience has shifted from emphasizing the product and materials to examining the dynamics of human feelings (Hassenzahl, 2008). Probing the user experience plays a central role, not only during the design process, but also during the regular ongoing

use of the product (Westerink, Van den Broek, Schut, & J., 2008).

To optimize the design process, the designer of a highly interactive product needs to know many different things about the user's physiological and cognitive processes. The designer needs to participate in a creative interaction with the user, and each should understand the needs of the other and how to communicate these needs (Sharp, Rogers, & Preece, 2007). Gathering a wealth of data about user lifestyles and attitudes helps researchers build a mental model of the users' real situation.

A number of studies have shown that capturing the user's experience as it happens can uncover the user's needs and be used to improve the design process (Koro-Ljungberg, Bussing, Williamson, & M'cormack-Hale, 2008). Researchers and designers have recognized the need for an assessment method; for a tool to obtain an accurate record of user life experiences that are the most important for judging the utility of a technology, and they have been exploring the potential value of incorporating user experiences into the development of new technology. Many design researchers prefer a phenomenological approach, and our method is best able to provide this (Hassenzahl, 2008).

The traditional information-recall method, relying on questionnaires and interviews, has the undeniable merit of offering valuable insights into the data collected, but also has some limitations. There are at least two problems to consider. The first is that the user's ability to provide an accurate account of the experience is limited and lacking in (Isomursu, Kuutti, & Väinämö, 2004; Stone, Shiffman, Atienza, & Nebeling, 2007); the second is that asking the user

to summarize past experiences over some period of time is asking for a reconstruction process influenced by a multitude of factors such as accuracy and completeness of recall, multiple biases and aggregation effects (Riediger, 2009). If we continue to use only traditional methods, important phenomena in user-oriented research cannot be adequately examined, especially the moment-by-moment contingencies and the dynamic user experience (Uy & Foo, 2010).

To avoid these deficiencies, several methods for acquiring data from human subjects in natural settings have been developed. ESM is a methodological approach that allows research participants to provide reports of their behavior and their cognitive and emotional states a number of times, just as they occur in the participants' natural environment (Joel M. Hektner, Schmidt, & Csikszentmihalyi, 2006; Stone, et al., 2007). The methodological advantages include mitigating memory (i.e., retrospective) biases, enhancing ecological validity, and capturing dynamic person-situation interactions over time (Schimmack & Diener, 2003). The conceptual benefits include providing a way to collect information about both the context and content of the daily life of the user (Joel M. Hektner & Csikszentmihalyi, 2002). A unique advantage of the ESM technique is not only that it provides information about the relationship between each subject individually, but also reveals those relationships that are common to a number of users. Today, the term experience sampling is used more broadly to refer to any naturalistic and repeated survey protocol (Conner, Tennen, Fleeson, & Barrett, 2009).

Technological innovations are creating new opportunities to capture accurate, real-time data with minimal intrusiveness. Initially, ESM tools focused on tool-specific responses or simply questionnaires on a PDA (Barrett & Barrett, 2001; Fischer, 2009). In recent years, the proliferation of ever more powerful media functions and mobile technologies has created opportunities for researchers to capture user experience in real time and in the actual situation of interest.

The increasingly affordable tools used in ESM, such as mobile phones, have evolved to allow greater ease of data collection for the participant, and they make ESM even more attractive to many researchers (Scollon, Kim-Prieto, & Diener, 2003). New technologies will enable extensions to ESM methodologies that combine continuous data collection on subject activities and physiological states with intermittent self-report data collection (Stone, et al., 2007).

Using ESM coupled with advanced mobile technology, researchers can expand upon the tried and true "experience sampling" research techniques and can capture the richness and environmental cues associated with more natural settings (Lew, 2009). Mobile devices can be used as aids for designers in the data collection process, to access user experience data, and to support the recording of notes in different formats such as text, photo, drawings, and audio note (Shahidi & Kasirun, 2009). Furthermore, the collected data offer a unique opportunity to follow user experiences and behaviors in their ecological context (Schwarz, 2007).

While early ESM, with the technology to collect user experiences, allowed significant attention to be paid to research issues related to device observables or focused on external contexts (location, time, the frequency of life activities) (Crabtree, Steve Benford, Paul Tennen, & Brown, 2006; Fischer, 2009), no large body of research literature has yet appeared that focuses on issues of internal context (emotions, thoughts, motivations and cognitive processes). Much exploration of this field remains to be done. The primary purpose of this study was to understand how the media used in different observational situations affect the self-reporting of subjects, and to clarify the full constellation of subject responses and behavior as they relate to conditions in the field.

METHOD

We provided a mobile phone application, Mobile Activity Probes 3 (Mobile AP3), based on the Android smart-phone platform, to support collecting data in different media formats for subject self-reporting in the form of notes (including photos), text, drawings and audio (Figure 1). The aim was to gather a rich

harvest of data from the field in order to gain an insight into the immediately perceived reality of the user's experience.

We chose to use the Google Nexus One, a smartphone that runs on the Android operating system, featuring GPS, Wi-Fi, 3G cellular network, a camera, and an accelerometer. Before distributing the phones to participants, we installed ESM, designed to automatically run on startup and then remain running in the background.

Figure 1. The multimedia format of notes

This application allows participants to record their moment-to-moment impressions, using different types of media. The tool is powerful and flexible enough to allow easy real-time data collection to avoid any recall bias. It maximizes ecological validity and communicates the real-world experience, so that the researchers can put themselves in the picture and feel the same influences experienced by the user.

The field research focuses on discrete episodes, which is appropriate when the phenomenon under study is conceptualized as occurring in discrete episodes. In this study, we use event-based sampling strategies to record the participants' responses to particular issues of interest(Stone, et al., 2007).

The analyses are based on a sample of 24 students (12 male, 12 female), ranging in age from 20 to 36 (M = 24.5 years). To ensure some homogeneity of social background, all subjects were selected from students in a university or graduate level media architecture-information design program.

Before testing, all participants filled in a questionnaire that asked about their professional experience with mobile utilization, the observation

of behavior and personal characteristics, the concept of the fieldwork and so on. This questionnaire enabled us to verify that the participants met the selection criteria and to gather additional data that might be of interest for subsequent analysis.

A two-phase study was designed, comprising the observation of the subject's environment (Phase 1) and observation of the human behaviors surrounding media note recording (Phase 2), with the aim of comparing the findings of these two phases(Figure 2). At each stage, participants were exposed to experiences of interest in the field, and observations were gathered over a one-hour period. We asked participants to make self-report notes using appropriate media (voice, short text messages, photos, and drawings) for the current in-the-field situation, to describe what was being watched or noticed(Figure 3).

To understand how the software was used in the field study, following each test the participants were asked to fill out a questionnaire about the relationship between the tool, the application software, and issues important to the study.

Figure 2. The experiment flow of data collection procedure.

Figure 3. Fieldwork photos and screen shots of a multiple recorded notes.

Furthermore, to gain a better understanding of the recorded notes, we listed the recorded notes on paper and the subject was asked to supplement the recorded information about their momentary experiences and activities at that time (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The paper format of listed the recorded notes.

RESULTS:

To understand how Mobile AP3 was used for self-report notes with different media, we analyzed the collected notes and questionnaire data. This study showed a striking effect of gender, and observation issues on the media type used for notes in our test. The recorded note quantitative results showcased in this report are from a controlled experiment involving 24 students (12 male, 12 female). Statistical significance was analyzed with a standard t-test, with alpha of 0.05 unless otherwise specified. The main metric used was the difference in pre- and post-test scores, as determined by the number of

notes made. The graphs in Figures 5 and 6 show the mean values for these for various media notes, classified by gender. The test was significant, $t(28) = 2.43, p = 0.02$.

Figure 5. The recorded note quantitative by gender group

In the aggregated results (Figure 5), the difference in the number of media notes in the two-phase study (the observation of environment and human behaviors) was shown by analysis of variance (ANOVA) to be meaningfully different between the two phases (Figure 5). The Tukey test showed that there was a significant difference between the observations of the environment and observations of human behaviors ($F(1,24) = 9.32, p < .01$). We also noted that there were significant media notes differences between photo notes and text, audio, and sketch notes ($F(1,24) = 5.41, p < .05$).

Figure 6. The recorded note quantitative by observation of the subject's environment (Phase 1) and observation of the human behaviors (Phase 2)

In the post-study questionnaire, the results of using a mobile device to support ESM presented a mixed picture. To summarize the salient features of the analysis, several findings are useful.

First, the technique enabled participants to use different media to make notes about their awareness. It encouraged the users to freely express their emotions and feelings.

Second, having the subjects make their reports using different types of notes gave us a deeper appreciation of their inner thoughts and the feelings behind their activities, which might otherwise have remained hidden.

Moreover, the auto tagging of time and location for each recorded note can reveal important time-based or event-based parameters of personality that can provide an estimate of a person's typical or average response over a period of time.

The field study showed that for Mobile AP3 to completely replace traditional tools such as pencil-and-paper notes would still be very challenging, but might be possible if certain prerequisites are fulfilled. First, most subjects felt that text input was not easy to use, especially when observing human behavior. Capturing and recording the complete flow of experience was often difficult, and many participants were unable to produce notes detailed enough to provide the desired level of rich information about their experience.

Second, in this study our test device screen was inadequate, it was too difficult to see in the sunshine, so some of the recorded notes provided little added information and the content quality was notably inferior.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS:

ESM with mobile tools is an ecologically valid user study technique that records data that not only captures emotions, motivations and cognitive processes, but also records them at the moment they occur by allowing participants to describe their own experiences. Additionally, ESM that uses mobile technology has evolved to allow greater ease of data collection for the researchers as well as the participants.

In this exploratory project, we examined the design of a smart-phone application for the SEM method. The application was validated as a self-reporting tool and evaluated in terms of the different media available. The application is functional and capable of recording observer reports. Additionally, we examined the relationship between objective observations and the different media notes used. Using a mobile phone to capture participants' momentary experiences provides the researcher with very rich, dynamic information about the users' daily lives.

The field of interactive design would benefit from more numerous and more rigorous empirical studies that assess how users think, feel, and what motivates them as they experience their natural environment. Moreover, important advances in analyzing the collected data are needed (Uy & Foo, 2010).

As mobile technology evolves, ESM is transforming data-gathering into an on-line event.

There are still many subjects for research in this field. We believe that there will be a widespread use of mobile devices to create and share collections of user situational responses with digital media. We are hopeful that future research will enhance the functionality and integrate more media recording modes so that one note can incorporate different media types, possibly better differentiating subjects' responses, which would be useful in field work.

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